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NON-TRADITIONAL FREE-FORM IN ARCHITECTURE PARAMETRIC DESIGN

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Abstract

Free-form architecture is a design approach that deviates from conventional, rectilinear forms and instead incorporates irregular, organic shapes and curves. It emphasises the importance of fluidity, motion, and sculptural qualities, using advanced computational tools and fabrication techniques to realise complex forms. One of the key advantages of free-form architecture is its ability to create unique and memorable buildings that stand out in the urban landscape. Free-form shapes allow architects to design buildings that are not limited by traditional geometric constraints, resulting in visually striking structures that can evoke a sense of wonder and awe in viewers. Additionally, using parametric design tools and digital fabrication techniques allows for greater precision and customization, enabling architects to create complex shapes that would be difficult to achieve through traditional construction methods. Our contribution to this topic was creating free-form geometry through parametric programming using the Grasshopper inside Rhino software presented for each category. After preparing the script, we printed the physical models based on the scripts by 3D printing.

Keywords: Grid Shells, Biomimicry, Topology, Form-Finding, Parametric Design, Tessellation, Voronoi Design.

1. INTRODUCTION

By observing nature and the surrounding world, the spectator may discover that the only straight lines that surround him are those established by a man. The period of cubism, constructivism, and functionalism was the perfection of the time of straight lines and straightforward geometric shapes or Euclidean geometry in design. An attempt to free objects from shapes that are based on straight lines followed. One of the main representatives of this concept was in the latter part of the 20th century, the famous architect Le Corbusier with his celebrated quote "Form follows function", saying that the form is subordinated to the function.

Later, Le Corbusier's "Form follows function" was changed to Frei Otto's "Form follows force", which means the form is subject to the course of forces. In other words, the structure should dictate the form of the architecture, rather than the other way around. This idea was further developed in Otto's concept of "natural

architecture", which emphasized the use of lightweight materials and organic forms inspired by nature (Foster, B. 1998). He believed that by studying natural forms and processes, architects and engineers could create more efficient and sustainable structures that harmonize with their environment (Shawkat, S 2021).

Most of us became familiar with Euclidean geometry during our studies, but we never learned non-Euclidean geometry unless we started studying math or science. The freedom that architects have gained after liberating themselves from linear conventions is now leading to "geometric anarchy", manifested in the design of so-called "free form" geometry, which presents the modern mathematics of curved surfaces in contemporary architecture. Free-form shapes have no analogy in nature, and they cannot be exactly described mathematically (Schleicher, S., Lienhard, J., Fleischmann, M. 2010), (Otto, F., Trostel, R. 1967). Complex object geometries require a new approach in the engineering part of their design.

Enhancing form offers a novel way for artistic expression and the field of structural engineering. A particular task of construction form of non-conventional structures is form-finding. Physical modelling of structures was used in their work by builders such as António Gaudi, Heinz Isler, and Frei Otto.

With the development of computer technology, numerical methods based on finding the shape and modelling of the equilibrium state have also begun to develop geometrically nonlinear problems. Utilizing physical models, also known as form models, serves to depict the dynamic variability and visual charm inherent in non-traditional structures, allowing for the mastery of this fine art. Engaging in physical modelling represents a potent instrument for delving into three-dimensional structural configurations, introducing a fresh dimension, and facilitating a more straightforward understanding of the interplay between structure and form (Otto, F., Trostel, R. 1967),(Fuller, R.B., 1962).

Structural designers together with architects analyse, discuss, and improve to create new forms, whether traditional or parametric to invent progressive construction processes as well as production technologies and thus enrich our society with new designs.

2. GOAL

Non-conventional free-form geometry in architecture aims to explore new and innovative ways to create structures that are not limited by traditional geometric shapes. By incorporating the principles of tensegrity, tensile structures, grid shells, biomimicry, topology, tessellation, and Voronoi design. Architects can design structures that not only exhibit striking visual aesthetics but are also exceptionally functional and environmentally sustainable.

Grid shells, which are made up of a series of interconnected geometric shapes, can be used to create complex and intricate forms that are both structurally stable and visually stunning. Biomimicry, which draws inspiration from the natural world, can be used to create structures that are not only beautiful but also sustainable and efficient. Topology, tessellation, and Voronoi design, meanwhile, offer a range of geometric principles that can be used to create complex and intricate forms that are both visually striking and highly functional. By incorporating these principles into their designs, architects can create buildings that push the boundaries of conventional architecture and offer new and innovative solutions to the challenges of the built environment.

The primary objectives of our work can be concisely summarized as:

- Demonstrate the elegant creation of physical models for unconventional structures, including tensegrity systems, tensile membrane structures, and non-traditional free-form geometries, (suitable for use as interior design elements and in public spaces).
- Find a feasible form-finding geometry process in architecture.
- Analyse the process of thinking using parametric programming, and parameterization of free-form geometry.

3. FREE-FORM IN ARCHITECTURE

3.1 Grid Shells in Architecture

Grid shells are innovative and structurally efficient architectural design elements that offer several advantages and creative possibilities. Here are some of the advantages and creative design aspects of grid shells in architecture:

- **Lightweight and efficient:** Grid shells are typically lightweight and require less material to construct than traditional building structures, making them more environmentally friendly and cost-effective.
- **Versatility:** Grid shells can be tailored to accommodate diverse shapes and dimensions, rendering them a flexible preference for architects.
- **Durability:** Grid shells can withstand natural disasters such as earthquakes and high winds, making them a safer choice for buildings in areas prone to these types of events.
- **Aesthetics:** The complex and intricate patterns created by the grid structure can be visually stunning and enhance the overall design of the building.

Overall, grid shells offer several advantages and creative design possibilities that make them a popular choice for architects looking to create visually stunning and structurally efficient buildings as depicted in Figures 1a, 1b, and 1c (Shawkat, S. 2019).

Fig. 1a. Grid Shell Parametric Design.

(Model created by the authors)

Fig. 1b. Grid Shell Parametric Design
(Models created by the authors)

Fig. 1c. Grid Shell Parametric Design
(Models created by the authors)

3.2 Biomimicry Design

Biomimicry represents a design methodology that finds creative solutions for human problems by drawing inspiration from the natural world. Within the realm of architecture, biomimicry has gained growing prominence as designers aspire to construct buildings that possess not only visual appeal but also efficiency, sustainability, and resilience. By studying the natural world and its systems, architects can learn from billions of years of evolution and apply these principles to their designs. By studying the structures and materials found in nature, architects can design buildings that are stronger and more durable. For example, the design of the Bionic Tower in Shanghai was inspired by the structure of a bamboo stalk, which is known for its strength and flexibility. The building's structure can withstand earthquakes and high winds, making it more resilient in the face of natural disasters. Overall, biomimicry design in architecture offers a range of advantages, including sustainability, energy efficiency, and resilience. As architects continue to explore the natural world for inspiration, we can expect to see more innovative and inspiring buildings that are not only beautiful but also functional and sustainable (Figures 2a, and 2b).

Fig. 2a Biomimicry Parametric Design.
(Model created by the authors)

Fig. 2b. Biomimicry Design Parametric Design
(Models created by the authors)

3.3 Topology in Architecture

Topology constitutes a field within mathematics dedicated to the examination of space characteristics that remain unaltered through continuous alterations, including stretching, bending, and twisting. In recent years, topology has become an increasingly popular tool for architects and designers, as it offers a new way of thinking about space and form. The use of topology in architecture allows for the creation of complex, non-Euclidean forms that challenge our traditional understanding of space and geometry. By using topological principles, architects can create buildings and structures that are not limited by the constraints of traditional geometry, resulting in unique and innovative designs as shown in (Figures. 3a, and 3b). One of the creative advantages of using topology in architecture is the ability to create structures that are both aesthetically pleasing and functional. For example, the design of the Heydar Aliyev Center in Azerbaijan, by architect Zaha Hadid (Meades J. 2008), (Michaud J. 2012) uses topological principles to create a fluid, organic form that is both visually striking and functional. The building's curved surfaces and irregular shapes create a sense of movement and fluidity, while its efficient use of space allows for optimal functionality. Another advantage of using the topology in architecture is the ability to optimize the use of materials and minimize waste. By using topological principles to design structures, architects can create forms that require less material and energy to construct, resulting in more sustainable and efficient buildings. Overall, topology offers architects and designers a new way of thinking about space and form, allowing for the creation of unique and innovative designs that are both aesthetically pleasing and functional. As topology continues to gain popularity in the field of architecture, we can expect to see more creative and inspiring designs that challenge our traditional understanding of space and geometry (Pottmann, H. 2007), (Mathews, C.J. 1972).

Fig 3a. Topology Design.
(Model created by the authors)

Fig. 3b. Topology Parametric Design
(Models created by the authors)

3.4 Tessellation Design

Tessellation, which is sometimes referred to as tiling, is a mathematical concept centered around the arrangement of geometric shapes in a repeating pattern on a surface, ensuring there are no gaps or overlaps between them (Figures. 4a, and 4b). In architecture, tessellation has become an increasingly popular design technique, as it offers a range of advantages in terms of aesthetics, functionality, and sustainability. One of the advantages of tessellation design in architecture is the ability to create visually striking and cohesive designs. By using a repeating pattern of geometric shapes, architects can create a sense of order and unity in their designs, while also adding visual interest and complexity. This technique has been used in a variety of architectural styles, from ancient Islamic architecture to contemporary buildings like the Guggenheim Museum Bilbao, which features a tessellated titanium exterior.

Fig. 4a. Tessellation Design.
(Model created by the authors)

Fig. 4b. Tessellation Parametric Design
(Models created by the authors)

Tessellation design can also offer functional advantages in architecture, such as improved acoustics and thermal performance. By using regular and repeating shapes, architects can create surfaces that reflect and absorb sound predictably, leading to better acoustics in spaces like concert halls or lecture theatres. Moreover, tessellation can serve to enhance material utilization and minimize waste by enabling the efficient utilization of standardized building components. Another advantage of tessellation design in architecture is its potential for sustainability. By using a repeating pattern of modular units, architects can create buildings that are easy to disassemble and recycle, reducing the environmental impact of construction and demolition.

Overall, tessellation design offers a range of advantages in architecture, from improved aesthetics to functional and sustainable benefits.

3.5 Voronoi Design

Voronoi design, also known as Voronoi tessellation, is a geometric pattern that is created by dividing a surface into irregular, but interconnected polygons. In architecture, Voronoi's design has gained popularity due to its ability to create visually striking and functional designs (Figures 5a, and 5b). One of the advantages of Voronoi design in architecture is its ability to optimize the use of space and material. By using a Voronoi pattern, architects can create buildings that are more efficient in their use of materials and energy, leading to more sustainable and cost-effective designs. The Voronoi pattern can also be used to create facades that provide shading and natural ventilation, reducing the need for artificial cooling and heating (Pottmann, H. 2007), (Mohammed, D., A. 2017). Another advantage of Voronoi design in architecture is its ability to create unique and visually interesting buildings. The Voronoi pattern creates a complex and irregular geometry that is different from traditional geometric shapes, resulting in structures that are visually striking and aesthetically pleasing. This design technique has been used in a variety of architectural styles, from modernist buildings like the Gherkin in London to organic structures like the Eden Project in Cornwall. In addition to its functional and aesthetic advantages, Voronoi design has also been used in architectural research to optimize building performance. By using computer simulations to analyse the Voronoi pattern, architects can optimize the shape and size of the polygons to improve factors such as natural lighting, structural stability, and energy efficiency. Overall, Voronoi's design offers a range of advantages in architecture, from sustainability and efficiency to unique and visually interesting designs.

Fig. 5a. Voronoi Design.
(Model created by the authors)

Fig. 5b. Voronoi Parametric Design
(Models created by the authors)

4. CONCLUSION

Designing architecture is a fascinating process that requires a combination of creativity and professional knowledge to achieve a truly spectacular result. The goal of any architectural design is to create a structure that not only serves its intended purpose but also captures the imagination and inspires those who experience it. To achieve this, it is important to approach the design process with a creative mindset that is open to new ideas and possibilities. One way to achieve this is to think outside the box when it comes to architectural form. By experimenting with unconventional shapes and structures, architects can create truly unique and memorable buildings that stand out from the crowd. From curving walls and unusual angles to asymmetrical facades and unexpected materials, there are countless ways to push the boundaries of traditional architecture and create something truly remarkable.

We realized more than 80 models of unconventional forms, which are divided into five subcategories: grid shells, biomimicry design, topology, tessellation design, and Voronoi design. For each model from these subsets, we first created different form-finding scripts using visual programming involving the specialized software Rhino/Grasshopper and Kangaroo. Subsequently, we created the so-called waffles for 3D printing and laser cutting. To implement tessellation and Voronoi design, we also created a special script. Building a script involves defining the inputs (e.g. geometry, dimensions, materials), the operations or functions (e.g. creating the grid, applying loads, analysing the structure), and the outputs (e.g. visualizing the results, exporting the data). Overall, the process of creating a script using visual programming requires a combination of design skills, technical knowledge, and programming expertise.

The freeform designs of lightweight structures effectively illustrate the dual need to uphold structural integrity while simultaneously seeking avenues for expressing their aesthetic beauty. The results of our work can also be used in the schooling of architecture students, as well as in cooperation with colleagues from related fields, or they can inspire everyone who likes architecture and design.

In conclusion, grid shells, biomimicry design, topology, tessellation design, and Voronoi design are all innovative techniques that are increasingly being used in architecture to create functional, sustainable, and visually striking structures.

Grid shells are known for their efficiency in using materials and their ability to create large and lightweight structures, while biomimicry design draws inspiration from nature to create buildings that are optimized for

their environment. Topology offers a new way of thinking about space and form, resulting in unique and innovative designs, while tessellation design allows for the creation of visually striking and cohesive designs. Voronoi design, on the other hand, provides the ability to optimize the use of space and material while creating unique and visually interesting forms.

In the grand scheme of things, as the field of architecture progresses, we can anticipate an increasing influx of innovative developments and inspiring designs that make use of these techniques, resulting in geometries that are not only functional and efficient but also beautiful and inspiring.

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